

STATUS OF 10 YEARS OF PROGRESS OF PRADHAN MANTRI MUDRA YOJANA IN INDIA

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Abstract

The Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana is one such step taken by the government towards promoting trade and business. Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana is an initiative taken by the Indian Government to provide funds to micro and small-scale businesses and to improve the situation of unorganised, non-cooperative industries and the informal sector in the Indian market. It would create employment opportunities in the rural as well as urban areas. Mudra Yojana's USP is to provide funds to those who find difficulty raising funds from formal financial institutions and to provide them funds at the lowest cost, irrespective of their education, skills, and gender. So therefore, financial inclusion in MSMEs through this scheme will act as a game changer in the financial market and will boost the Indian economy in the near future. Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) continues to serve millions of unfunded micro-borrowers in the country with much-needed loans for their business activities, resulting in the upliftment of their lives. On 8 April 2025, India marks 10 years of the Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana (PMMY). Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) is the flagship programme of the prime minister aimed at funding the unfunded micro-enterprises and small businesses. By removing the burden of collateral and simplifying access, MUDRA laid the foundation for a new era of grassroots entrepreneurship. From stitching units and tea stalls to salons, mechanic shops, and mobile repair businesses, crores of micro-entrepreneurs have stepped forward with confidence, enabled by a system that believed in their potential. PMMY has supported these journeys by offering institutional credit to non-corporate, non-farm micro- and small enterprises that form the backbone of India's economy. This paper focuses on 10 years of progress of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana in India.

Introduction:

The Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana aims to fund the unfunded and plays the crucial role of serving as a lender of last resort. The main objective of this yojana is to provide loan assistance to small entrepreneurs, who are generally classified as micro units by the Government of India. These industries face inconvenience in getting funds from banks and financial institutions because of a lack of credibility due to the incomplete or non-maintenance of books of accounts on a regular basis and the non-fulfilment of taxation responsibilities. Therefore, to bridge the financial gap between entrepreneurs and the financing problem, the Government of India launched this scheme on April 8, 2015, which is popularly known as the Micro Units Development and Refinancing Agency (MUDRA). PMMY aims to provide financial inclusiveness and support to the marginalised and hitherto socio-economically neglected classes. PMMY has given wings to the dreams and aspirations of millions, along with a feeling of self-worth and independence. Need for the MUDRA Yojana India is a young country brimming with youthful enthusiasm and aspirations. In order to provide fertile ground for sowing the seeds of India's development, it is very important to harness the innovative zeal of young India, which can provide new-age solutions to existing gaps in the economic ecosystem of the country. Understanding the need to harness the latent potential of entrepreneurship in India, the Union Government launched the Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana.

There has been phenomenal growth in the Indian microfinance sector in the past 18 years. Banks and NBFCs have emerged as powerful means of transportation for providing financial assistance to

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micro- and small-sized enterprises. It is a commendable action taken by the government to improve the growth potential of small entrepreneurs.

MUDRA Yojana is a positive step taken by the Indian Government towards promoting economic growth and development as it engages in extending loans to small enterprises on easy terms. These small enterprises contribute to the GDP of our country and also assist in job creation. MUDRA Yojana aims to encourage small enterprise owners to grow their business operations and minimise their indebtedness by providing a basic system of credit. The Micro Units Development and Refinancing Agency Limited was initially a subsidiary of the Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI), which helps in providing finance, extensions, credit guarantees, and other support schemes. SIDBI is also responsible for the easy implementation and smooth functioning of the government's announced schemes. In the last 10 years, MUDRA has established itself as a key player in ensuring adequate focus on microenterprises and continues to encourage a culture of entrepreneurship.

MUDRA Vision

To be an integrated financial and support services provider par excellence, benchmarked with global best practices and standards, for the bottom of the pyramid universe for their comprehensive economic and social development.

MUDRA Mission

To create an inclusive, sustainable and value-based entrepreneurial culture in collaboration with our partner institutions in achieving economic success and financial security.

MUDRA Purpose

Our basic purpose is to attain development in an inclusive and sustainable manner by supporting and promoting partner institutions and creating an ecosystem of growth for the micro-enterprise sector.

Source: <https://www.pib.gov.in>

PMMY's overall goal is to support entrepreneurs through financial assistance and the creation of a strong entrepreneurial environment. It works towards this mission in three main stages:

1. Access to Finance: PMMY seeks to bridge the financial gap by extending affordable and accessible credit to micro and small enterprises. By offering collateral-free loans, the mission ensures that financial constraints do not impede the aspirations of budding entrepreneurs, thereby fostering a conducive environment for business growth.

2. Skill Enhancement and Capacity Building: Beyond mere financial assistance, PMMY is committed to nurturing a culture of entrepreneurship by providing training and skill development

programmes. This holistic approach aims to empower individuals with the knowledge and expertise required to manage and expand their enterprises, ensuring long-term sustainability.

3. Entrepreneurial Upliftment: At its core, PMMY endeavours to uplift the socio-economic status of individuals, particularly those at the grassroots level. By encouraging self-employment and enterprise creation, the mission seeks to bring about a positive transformation in the lives of beneficiaries, promoting inclusivity and reducing economic disparities. The Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) is a government scheme that supports aspiring entrepreneurs. It provides loans to small businesses and startups, helping them to start and grow their businesses. PMMY has had a significant impact on the Indian economy, creating jobs and boosting economic growth. However, there are also some challenges associated with the scheme, such as the lack of awareness among potential beneficiaries and the need for more efficient loan disbursement mechanisms.

“In a nation where dreams often outpace resources, the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) has emerged as a transformative bridge between ambition and opportunity.” Launched in 2015 as a flagship financial inclusion initiative under the mantra “Fund the Unfunded”, PMMY was envisioned to democratise access to institutional credit for micro and small enterprises, particularly among first-generation entrepreneurs.

Over its decade-long journey, the scheme has sanctioned over 52 crore loans amounting to ₹32.61 lakh crore, with 70% of beneficiaries being women and over half from SC/ST/OBC communities, making it a cornerstone of inclusive, grassroots-led economic empowerment.

This study examines the nuances of PMMY, including its impact, challenges, and potential areas for improvement.

Need for the study

Based on its 10th anniversary in April 2025, a study of the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) is needed to evaluate its long-term impact, assess the scheme's sustainability, and identify challenges for future improvements

. A decade of data offers a critical opportunity to move beyond initial statistics and analyze the deeper socio-economic changes brought about by the scheme.

Key reasons for a 10-year study

1. Analyze long-term economic impact

Move beyond micro-level to macro-level impact: While initial reports track loan disbursements, a 10-year study can analyze if the scheme has genuinely stimulated significant grassroots economic activity and job creation across different regions. The government estimates 10 crore jobs were created, which requires a deeper, independent analysis.

Shift from micro to small enterprises: With the growth in Kishor (₹50,000–₹5 lakh) and Tarun (₹5 lakh–₹10 lakh) loans, a study can confirm if Mudra successfully helps entrepreneurs scale their businesses and not just survive at a subsistence level.

Impact on formalization: Research can investigate if the collateral-free credit has helped micro-enterprises formalize by integrating them into the banking system, creating credit histories, and moving away from informal, high-cost lenders.

2. Assess sustainability and identify weaknesses

Evaluate Non-Performing Assets (NPAs): Independent analysis is needed to assess repayment health beyond government figures. Concerns over rising NPAs and repayment stress suggest a need to study how factors like financial literacy, business viability, and credit assessment practices affect loan repayment.

Examine regional disparities: Despite broad outreach, data shows uneven disbursement across states and low participation in some regions. A study can identify the systemic reasons for this disparity and suggest strategies for more equitable credit access.

Prevent misuse of funds: Concerns have been raised about loans being diverted for personal use rather than business growth. Research is needed to evaluate the effectiveness of monitoring mechanisms and provide recommendations for better oversight.

3. Analyze inclusive growth metrics

Evaluate women's economic empowerment: With women constituting 68% of beneficiaries, research can examine if Mudra loans have empowered women entrepreneurs, improved their economic independence, and addressed gender gaps in finance.

Measure benefits for marginalized groups: A study can determine if the scheme has met its goal of including marginalized communities (SC/ST/OBC) in the financial mainstream and assess the quality of support they receive.

4. Inform future policy and support systems

Shift focus from lending to business development: A decade of experience highlights that credit alone is not enough for sustainable growth. A study can provide recommendations on integrating non-financial support, such as business training, market linkages, and digital literacy, into the scheme.

Improve credit assessment and borrower education: Research can lead to improved credit evaluation processes that balance risk with the scheme's inclusive goals. Additionally, a study can inform the development of targeted financial literacy programs to improve credit management among small borrowers.

Leverage new technologies: With new categories like "Tarun Plus" extending limits, a study can analyze evolving credit demand and suggest leveraging technology to improve access and transparency.

Overdraft facility

In addition, the overdraft amount of Rs. 5,000 sanctioned under PMJDY has also been classified as a Mudra loan.

Microcredit Scheme: In this scheme, loans have been provided up to one lakh rupees through Microfinance Institutions for various microenterprises. The model of providing loans may be through self-help groups, joint liability groups, or individuals.

Mudra Card: A debit card provided to the Mudra loan account for availing working capital loans. Therefore, the loanee has to manage the working capital limit in a cost-efficient manner and keep the interest burden at a minimum.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Shiny (2017) opined that Mudra Yojana can encourage more entrepreneurs to come up with creative business ideas, which can lead to the development of the Indian economy. MUDRA can act as an ideal regulator to collectivise and coordinate all the financial institutions in the micro- and small-business sectors under one umbrella. The study anticipates that MUDRA will take on the role of a

development agency for providing credit services and other related services to small and micro enterprises.

Godha and Nama (2017), keeping the major objective of "Fund the Unfunded," opine that PMMY is a new financial inclusion initiative by the Government of India. The study focused on the role, progress, and achievement level of PMMY in the state of Rajasthan. The MUDRA scheme was successful in terms of the number of sanctioned loans and its disbursement to small and micro enterprises in the state of Rajasthan during FY 2015-16 and FY 2016-17.

George and Nalini (2018) focused on the lead role played by the MUDRA Bank in the growth of MSMEs. The study also analysed the performance of the MUDRA bank in Kerala and found that the MUDRA bank was successful in the delivery of MUDRA products and the disbursement of the sanctioned amount with little delay.

Mahajan (2018) analysed the impact and performance of the Mudra Yojana under the PMMY in 2016 on small business owners and self-employed people. Descriptive statistical tools were used to analyse the data collected from the secondary sources. Region-wise analysis of PMMY shows that all four regions have received wide coverage, but the south region has gotten the most benefit this year. Individual bank-wise performance shows that the State Bank of India stands first among all of the banks in terms of disbursement of MUDRA loans in the year. The study concludes that if the products derived from the MUDRA scheme can earn foreign currency, then it can improve the demand for Indian rupees in the international trade market.

Ali. M.S. (2019) discusses the salient features of the MUDRA loan scheme, the procedure for loan sanction by the bank under the MUDRA scheme, achievements or milestones under the MUDRA loan scheme, NPAs in the MUDRA scheme, etc., which are explained. The important aspect of the study is to examine the banker's perspective with special reference to the problems faced by them in managing MUDRA lending. The suggestion given by the author is that for the assessment of credit needs, it should be mandatory for them to submit audited financial statements and calculate financial ratios while providing working capital and term loans under the MUDRA scheme.

Statement of the problem

In the decade since its launch in April 2015, the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) has become a crucial government initiative aimed at providing collateral-free institutional credit to non-corporate, non-farm micro and small enterprises in India. The scheme has disbursed over 52 crore loans worth more than ₹32.6 lakh crore as of April 2025, promoting financial inclusion, particularly for women and marginalized communities. MSME lending has significantly increased, with its share in total bank credit growing from 15.8% in FY14 to nearly 20% in FY24

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the current status and progress of PMMY.
2. To explain the achievements of the last ten years of PMMY.
3. To describe an overview of the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana.
4. To find out the challenges of the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana

Research Methodology

This study is descriptive in nature. The study is based on secondary data sources. The data has been collected from various offline and online sources, which include the annual reports of the Government of India, books, articles, and the official website of Mudra, the Government of India. The focus is on identifying the current state of MUDRA lending and the growth trend it has set since its inception under the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana. The data collected is secondary in nature and has been collected from various annual reports published by PMMY from 2015–16 to 2023–24.

Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana

The Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana (PMMY) was launched on April 8, 2015, by Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi with the aim of facilitating easy collateral-free microcredit of up to ₹10 lakh to non-corporate, non-farm small and micro entrepreneurs for income-generating activities. The PMMY

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aims to enable microfinance institutions (MFIs), non-banking financial institutions and companies (NBFCs), small finance banks, RBRs, commercial banks, cooperative banks, etc. to provide low-rate loans to eligible entities.

PMMY Eligibility

To avail of the benefits of the PMMY Scheme, the person should be a citizen of India. The loans are basically for people having a business plan in a Non-Farming Sector with Income generating activities like the following:

- ❖ Manufacturing
- ❖ Processing
- ❖ Trade
- ❖ Service Sector
- ❖ Or any other fields whose credit demand is less than 10 lakhs.

The Indian Citizen seeking MUDRA Loans under the PMMY Scheme will have to approach either an MFI, Bank or NBFC to avail it.

Objectives of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana

- **Funding the unfunded** – To sanction loans up to rupees 10 Lakhs to those who have a business plan to generate income from a non-farm activity like manufacturing, processing, trading, or service sector but don't have enough capital to invest
- **Reducing jobless economic growth** – To help generate sources of employment and increase the overall GDP by providing micro-enterprises with credit facilities.
- **Monitoring and regulating the Microfinance institutions (MFI)** – With the help of MUDRA bank, the network of microfinance institutions will be monitored and new registration will also be done.
- **Integration of Informal economy into Formal sector** – It will help India also grow its tax base as incomes from the informal sector are non-taxed.
- **Promoting financial inclusion** – PMMY further adds to the vision of financial inclusion with the aim to reach the last mile credit delivery to micro-businesses and taking the help of technology solutions.

Types of PMMY Loans

The Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) has three products as per the funding requirements of the Beneficiary or the Entrepreneur. MUDRA has created three products i.e. 'Shishu', 'Kishore' and 'Tarun' as per the stage of growth and funding needs of the beneficiary micro unit.

Name of the Type of Loan	Coverage of the Loan
<i>Shishu</i>	Covering loans up to Rs. 50,000.
<i>Kishor</i>	Covering loans above Rs. 50,000 and up to Rs. 5 lakh.
<i>Tarun</i>	Covering loans above Rs. 5 lakh and up to Rs. 10 lakh.

The rates of interests under these schemes are as follows:

- **Shishu Yojana** – Interest charged is around 10% to 12%, where public sector banks generally charge at very reasonable rate.
- **Kishore Yojana** – Interest charged is around 14% to 17% and differs from bank to bank.
- **Tarun Yojana** – the rate of Interest charged under this scheme starts from 16%.

MUDRA Yojana is like a NBFC which provides funds to small enterprises of the country. It also provides refinance facility to Banks/MFIs so that they can further lend money to micro units up to the limit of 10,00,000.

Sectors Covered under PMMY

To maximize coverage of beneficiaries and tailor products to meet requirements of specific business activities, sector/activity focused schemes would be rolled out. To begin with, based on the higher concentration of businesses in certain activities/sectors, schemes are proposed for:

Sector	Comments	Types of Activities under that Sector
Land Transport Sector	Loans to support the purchase of transport vehicles. These vehicles could be used for goods or personal transport.	Auto-rickshaws, E- rickshaws, etc. Passenger cars and taxis. Small-goods transport vehicles. Other three-wheelers.
Service Sector	This includes community services, social services, or personal services.	Hair and beauty salons, beauty parlours, etc. Tailoring stores, boutiques, dry cleaning services, etc. Gymnasium, Athletic training, medical shops, etc. Garage, Cycle & motorcycle repair centres, etc. Other services like photocopying shops, courier agencies, etc.
Food Product Sector	Support for small scale food industries.	Manufacturing papads, pickles, jams/jellies, and other agricultural produce/preservation methods. Sweet shops, small service food centres, etc. Everyday catering services, canteens, etc. Micro cold storages, ice-making factories, Cold chain vehicles, ice cream making industries, etc. Bakeries and Baked products manufacturing
Textile Sector	Supporting micro textile industries that produce garment and non-garment products	Handloom and power loom industry Handwork industry like embroidery, chikan work, dyeing and printing, knitting, etc. Mechanical or computerized stitching for garments and non-garments. Production of automobile and furnishing accessories, etc

Steps taken to improve implementation of the scheme:

- Handholding support for facilitating the submission of loan applications
- Provision for online applications through PSBloansin59minutes and the Udyamimitra portal
- Intensive publicity campaigns for increased visibility of the scheme amongst the stakeholders
- Simplification of application forms
- Nomination of MUDRA Nodal Officers in Public Sector Banks (PSBs)
- Periodic monitoring of the performance of PSBs with regard to PMMY

The current status of PMMY in India

The Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana (PMMY) was launched on April 8, 2015, by Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi with the aim of facilitating easy collateral-free microcredit of up to ₹10 lakh to

non-corporate, non-farm small and micro entrepreneurs for income-generating activities. The loans under PMMY are provided by Member Lending Institutions (MLIs), i.e., banks, non-banking financial companies (NBFCs), microfinance institutions (MFIs), and other financial intermediaries.

Upon marking the successful 10th anniversary of the PMMY, As India celebrates the 10th anniversary of the Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana (PMMY), Prime Minister Narendra Modi extended his heartfelt congratulations to the beneficiaries of the scheme, highlighting its transformative impact on millions of lives across the country. In a series of post on X, the Prime Minister expressed his pride in the success of MUDRA, which has played a pivotal role in empowering marginalized communities, fostering entrepreneurship, and driving inclusive economic growth in India.

“Today, as we mark #10YearsOfMUDRA, I would like to congratulate all those whose lives have been transformed thanks to this scheme. Over this decade, MUDRA Yojana has turned several dreams into reality, empowering people who were previously overlooked with the financial support to shine. It illustrates that for the people of India, nothing is impossible!” said Prime Minister Modi. The PM also emphasized the scheme’s focus on social inclusion, noting that nearly half of MUDRA beneficiaries come from the SC, ST, and OBC communities, while more than 70% of the beneficiaries are women. “Every Mudra loan carries with it dignity, self-respect, and opportunity. In addition to financial inclusion, this scheme has also ensured social inclusion and economic freedom,” he added.

Since its launch on April 8, 2015, the Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana has sanctioned over 52 crore loans, totaling ₹32.61 lakh crore. The average loan size has grown significantly, from ₹38,000 in FY16 to ₹1.02 lakh in FY25, reflecting the increasing demand for higher-value loans among small enterprises.

The scheme has played a key role in the rise of credit flow to Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). According to a report by the State Bank of India, MSME lending surged from ₹8.51 lakh crore in FY14 to ₹27.25 lakh crore in FY24, with projections indicating it will exceed ₹30 lakh crore in FY25. The share of MSME credit in total bank credit has increased from 15.8% in FY14 to nearly 20% in FY24, underscoring the growing importance of MSMEs in India’s economy.

Women have been significant beneficiaries of the MUDRA scheme, with women accounting for 68% of the total recipients. The average loan for women has risen at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 13%, reaching ₹62,679 between FY16 and FY25. Women-led MSMEs, particularly in states with higher proportions of loans to women, have seen notable increases in employment generation, according to government data.

MUDRA has also made substantial strides in ensuring expanded access to formal finance for traditionally underserved groups. Fifty percent of MUDRA accounts are held by entrepreneurs from SC, ST, and OBC communities, while 11% of accounts are held by members of minority communities.

Loan disbursements under MUDRA have seen a remarkable shift toward larger loans. Loans in the Kishor category (₹50,000 to ₹5 lakh) grew from just 5.9% of total disbursements in FY16 to 44.7% in FY25. Additionally, loans in the Tarun category (₹5 lakh to ₹10 lakh) and the newly introduced Tarun Plus category (₹10 lakh to ₹20 lakh) have also witnessed increased demand.

Tamil Nadu leads in total disbursements, with ₹3.23 lakh crore, followed closely by Uttar Pradesh (₹3.14 lakh crore) and Karnataka (₹3.02 lakh crore). Other states, including West Bengal and Bihar, have also seen substantial contributions. Among Union Territories, Jammu and Kashmir has recorded ₹45,815.92 crore across over 21 lakh loan accounts.

MUDRA caters to micro enterprises engaged in a variety of sectors, including manufacturing, trading, processing, and services. These small businesses often sole proprietorships or own-account enterprises employ nearly 10 crore people, making them the second-largest source of employment in India after agriculture.

The scheme has garnered global recognition for its contribution to expanding financial access and promoting entrepreneurship. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) has praised MUDRA for supporting self-employment and the formalization of the economy. The IMF’s 2024 report reaffirms

the significant role of schemes like PMMY in fostering the growth of women-led businesses and enhancing financial inclusion.

The MUDRA Yojana is implemented through a network of lending institutions, including Scheduled Commercial Banks, Regional Rural Banks, Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs), and Microfinance Institutions. These institutions offer collateral-free loans of up to ₹20 lakh under the scheme, which operates under the Micro Units Development and Refinance Agency (MUDRA).

Status of 10 Years of Progress of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana in India

Over the first ten years of its implementation, the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) has been a key driver of financial inclusion and grassroots entrepreneurship in India. Launched on April 8, 2015, the scheme has provided collateral-free loans to micro and small non-farm enterprises, with significant achievements in credit outreach, women's empowerment, and formalization of the MSME sector.

Key achievements over 10 years (2015–2025)

1. Expansive credit outreach

- **Total loans:** The PMMY has sanctioned and disbursed over 52 crore loans, with a cumulative value exceeding ₹32.61 lakh crore.
- **First-time borrowers:** Over 100 million first-time entrepreneurs have accessed formal credit through the scheme.
- **Average loan size:** The average ticket size of loans has nearly tripled, growing from ₹38,000 in FY16 to ₹1.02 lakh in FY25, indicating a scaling-up of businesses.
- **MSME credit growth:** The scheme has fueled a significant boom in credit flow to the MSME sector. MSME lending rose from ₹8.51 lakh crore in FY14 to ₹27.25 lakh crore in FY24, with its share of total bank credit growing from 15.8% to nearly 20%.

2. Focus on social inclusion

- **Empowering women:** Women have emerged as the biggest beneficiaries, accounting for 68% of all Mudra loans. From FY16 to FY25, the average loan amount disbursed to women increased at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 13%.
- **Backward communities:** The scheme has promoted access to formal finance for marginalized communities, with 50% of accounts held by SC, ST, and OBC entrepreneurs.

3. Maturing credit demand

- **Shift to larger loans:** The scheme has seen a progressive shift in loan categories over the decade. The share of entry-level 'Shishu' loans (up to ₹50,000) has decreased, while higher-value 'Kishor' (₹50,000–₹5 lakh) and 'Tarun' (₹5 lakh–₹10 lakh) loans have gained significant momentum, indicating business growth and scaling.
- **Increased loan limit:** The government raised the Mudra loan limit to ₹20 lakh in the 2024–25 Union Budget for entrepreneurs who have successfully repaid previous loans, introducing a new 'Tarun Plus' category.

4. Uneven regional spread

- **Top performers:** As of February 2025, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, and Karnataka lead in total loan disbursements, highlighting strong uptake in key states.
- **Untapped potential:** Some regions, particularly states in the northeast and certain Union Territories like Lakshadweep, have seen lower disbursements, pointing to room for further expansion.

5. Associated challenges

- **Non-performing assets (NPAs):** A portion of Mudra loans has turned into NPAs. While the average default rate is reportedly lower than at public sector banks, it remains a challenge that requires tightening scrutiny and better credit evaluation.
- **Beyond credit:** While the scheme has excelled at providing credit access, some experts suggest that borrowers could benefit from additional support in business training and market access to ensure sustainable growth.

Achievements under Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana

Since its launch in April 2015, the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) has sanctioned over 52 crore loans worth ₹32.61 lakh crore, fuelling a nationwide entrepreneurial revolution. Business growth is no longer confined to big cities—it is spreading to small towns and villages, where first-time entrepreneurs are taking charge of their destinies. The shift in mindset is evident: people are no longer job seekers; they are becoming job creators.

Source: <https://www.pib.gov.in>

MSME Credit Boom: A Stronger Business Ecosystem

The SBI report highlights a significant rise in credit flow to MSMEs, driven by Mudra’s impact. MSME lending surged from ₹8.51 lakh crore in FY14 to ₹27.25 lakh crore in FY24, and is projected to cross ₹30 lakh crore in FY25. The share of MSME credit in total bank credit increased from 15.8 percent in FY14 to nearly 20 percent in FY24, showcasing its growing role in the Indian economy. This expansion has enabled businesses in smaller towns and rural areas to access financial support that was previously unavailable, strengthening India’s self-reliant economy and driving grassroots job creation.

Source: <https://www.pib.gov.in>

Financial Inclusion: Empowering Women

Women account for 68 percent of all Mudra beneficiaries, underscoring the scheme’s pivotal role in advancing women-led enterprises across the country. Between FY16 and FY25, the per woman PMMY disbursement amount increased at a CAGR of 13 percent, reaching ₹62,679, while per woman incremental deposits grew at a CAGR of 14 percent to ₹95,269. States with higher disbursement shares to women have recorded significantly higher employment generation through women-led MSMEs, reinforcing the effectiveness of targeted financial inclusion in enhancing women’s economic empowerment and labour force participation.

Source: <https://www.pib.gov.in>

Financial Inclusion: Reaching Socially Marginalised Groups

PMMY has made significant progress in breaking traditional credit barriers. According to the SBI report, 50 percent of Mudra accounts are held by SC, ST and OBC entrepreneurs, ensuring wider access to formal finance. Furthermore, 11 percent of Mudra loan holders belong to minority communities, demonstrating the scheme's contribution to inclusive growth by enabling marginalised communities to become active participants in the formal economy.

Progressive Lending: From Shishu to Tarun

Over the past ten years, Mudra has facilitated the opening of over 52 crore loan accounts, marking a steady rise in entrepreneurial activity. The share of Kishor loans (₹50,000 to ₹5 lakh) has grown from 5.9 percent in FY16 to 44.7 percent in FY25, indicating a shift from micro to small enterprises. The Tarun category (₹5 lakh to ₹10 lakh) is also gaining momentum, proving that Mudra is not just about starting businesses but helping them scale.

Source: <https://www.pib.gov.in>

Bigger Loans, Stronger Businesses

A telescopic view of total loans sanctioned and disbursed under PMMY reveals that the scheme's Unique Selling Proposition has been well received by a diverse base of intended beneficiaries, thereby strengthening the economic influence of the bottom of the pyramid.

The average ticket size of loans has nearly tripled rising from ₹38,000 in FY16 to ₹72,000 in FY23, and further to ₹1.02 lakh in FY25—reflecting growing economies of scale and a deepening of both market depth and width.

Furthermore, loan disbursement rose by 36 percent in FY23, indicating a strong revival of entrepreneurial confidence across the country.

Source: <https://www.pib.gov.in>

Leading States/UTs in Mudra Loan Disbursal

As of February 28, 2025, since the launch of the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana in 2015, Tamil Nadu has recorded the highest disbursement among states at ₹3,23,647.76 crore. Uttar Pradesh follows with ₹3,14,360.86 crore, while Karnataka ranks third with ₹3,02,146.41 crore. West Bengal and Bihar have also seen significant disbursements of ₹2,82,322.94 crore and ₹2,81,943.31 crore respectively. Maharashtra stands sixth at ₹2,74,402.02 crore, reflecting the scheme's broad reach and impact across key states over the past decade.

Source: <https://www.pib.gov.in>

Among Union Territories, Jammu and Kashmir leads with a total disbursement of ₹45,815.92 crore across 21,33,342 loan accounts. The figures underscore the role of the scheme in expanding access to credit and promoting self-employment, not just across states but also in Union Territories.

Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana: Continuing Support to the Bottom of the Pyramid

Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY), the flagship programme of the Prime Minister aimed at funding unfunded microenterprises and small businesses, completed eight years of operations. Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY), the flagship programme of the Prime Minister aimed at funding unfunded microenterprises and small businesses, completed 9 years of its operations, extending a cumulative amount of ₹22.89 lakh crore under the programme to ₹41.16 crore loan

accounts, primarily benefiting the borrowers of weaker sections of society. The lending institutions, which include all the public sector banks, private sector banks, regional rural banks, small finance banks, micro-finance institutions (MFIs), and non-banking financial companies (NBFCs), have together exceeded the annual targets set out by the Government of India under PMMY every year.

**Table no.1 PMMY Financial year wise Target Vs Achievement
(Amount. In Rs. Lakh crore)**

Financial Year	Target	Achievement
2015-16	1.22	1.37
2016-17	1.80	1.80
2017-18	2.44	2.53
2018-19	3.00	3.21
2019-20	3.25	3.37
2020-21	3.50	3.21
2021-22	3.06	3.39
2022-23	4.40	4.50
2023-24	5.00	5.32

Source: Annual Report 2023-24 of Mudra. Government of India.

From Table 1 above, it can be inferred that there has been an almost continuous growth in the sanctioned and disbursed amounts of MUDRA loans. The financial year 2020–21 has been an exception to this effect, mainly because of a decline in economic activity in the entire country due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The total amount disbursed under this scheme was lowest during FY 2015-16 at Rs. 1.37 lakh crores. As the scheme gained popularity, it showed positive growth during the entire period under review. As of now, the highest total funds disbursed stand at Rs. 5.32 lakh crores during FY 2023–24. Initially, PMMY covered income-generating activities in the manufacturing, trading, and services sectors only. Since FY 2016–17, loans for agriculture-allied activities such as dairy, poultry, livestock rearing, beekeeping, agri-clinics, etc. that promote livelihood have been included in PMMY. In FY 2017–18, loans for financing tractors and power tillers were also included in PMMY. In FY 2018–19, loans for the purchase of two-wheelers for commercial purposes have also been brought under PMMY. The average ticket size of the loans has nearly doubled to Rs. 72,000 in FY 2022–23 from Rs. 38,000 in FY 2015–16. It shows the increasing share of borrowers under the Kishor and Tarun categories of PMMY.

Micro Units Development & Refinance Agency Ltd. (MUDRA), as a support institution, has played a dual role by extending refinance support to various lending institutions and monitoring the progress of implementation of PMMY closely through a dedicated portal that captures various aggregated data pertaining to the scheme as per the requirements of the Government of India. The PMMY programme, during the last six years, has benefited 29.55 crore loan accounts with a sanction of 15.52 lakh crore, thus enabling the grass-roots economy of the country to contribute in a bigger way to the overall economic growth of the nation. The target set by the Government of India for disbursements under PMMY for the years 2022–2023 was 4.50 lakh crore, under PMMY for the years 2023–2024 was 5.32 lakh crore which was distributed across various lending institutions, viz., banks, MFIs, and NBFCs, based on their outreach and presence in various parts of the country.

Loan Category Analysis: Mudra loans are extended in three categories based on the size of the loans. They are Shishu (up to 50,000), Kishor (above 50,000 and up to 5 lakh), and Tarun (above 5 lakh and up to 10 lakh). The share of the three categories of PMMY has been analysed and is given below in the table

The progress under PMMY during past 9 years is as under.

Table 2: Nine years of Categorization of MUDRA Loans from F.Y. 2016-17 to 2023-24

Financial Year	SHISHU		KISHORE		TARUN	
	Accounts (In Lakhs)	TotalAmount Sanctioned (Rs. Crores)	Accounts (In Lakhs)	TotalAmount Sanctioned (Rs. Crores)	Accounts (In Lakhs)	TotalAmount Sanctioned (Rs. Crores)
2015-16	324.01	62894.96	20.69	43052.55	4.10	31501.76
2016-17	364.98	85100.74	26.63	53545.14	5.40	41882.66
2017-18	426.69	106001.60	46.53	86732.16	8.07	60943.34
2018-19	515.07	142345.25	66.06	104386.68	17.57	74990.86
2019-20	544.91	163559.00	64.72	95578.00	12.85	78359.00
2020-21	401.80	109953.00	94.86	132516.00	10.69	79290.00
2021-22	417.21	123969.05	110.88	133389.24	9.86	74043.91
2022-23	430.78	141609.85	179.16	200936.63	13.16	107877.18
2023-24	416.28	1,47,784.68	2,36.30	2,57,094.50	15.17	1,27,479.17
Total	3841.73	935433.45	609.53	850136.4	96.87	548888.71

Source: Annual Reports of Mudra. Government of India

The above table 2 shows the breakdown of the three categories of MUDRA loans in terms of the number of accounts opened and the total amount sanctioned over the period ranging between FY 2015–16 and FY 2022–23. The highest share, in terms of both the number of loan accounts and the total amount sanctioned, is for the Shishu category, followed by Kishor and Tarun.

It clearly shows that the number of small-scale entrepreneurs is the highest among all categories of borrowers. In the Shishu category, there has been an increase both in terms of the number of loan accounts and the total amount sanctioned over the study period, except for FY 2020–21, which saw a negative growth. This is primarily due to the COVID-19 pandemic, when most of the economic activity was brought to a standstill. In the Kishor category, there has been almost consistent growth, with a continuous increase in both the number of loan accounts and the total amount sanctioned in the period ranging from FY 2015-16 to FY 2017-18. FY 2019–20 saw a momentary fall both in terms of the number of loan accounts and the total amount sanctioned, but since FY 2020–21, both variables have shown a considerable rise. In the Tarun category, there has been an increase in the number of loan accounts in the period ranging between FY 2016–17 and FY 2018–19; however, it has shown a consistent fall since FY 2019–20. In terms of total amount sanctioned, there has been an increase in the period ranging between FY 2016–17 and 2020–21. In FY 2021–22, there was a fall in the total amount sanctioned, but the sanction amount rose in the financial year 2023–24.

Out of the total amount disbursed, 41.76% went to the women borrowers with 63.63% of the total accounts belonged to women. The reason for high share of women is lending of micro-loans by the MFIs primarily to women. The share of the weaker section (SC/ST/OBCs) borrowers of the society in the PMMY programme was 46.94% in terms of loan accounts, and 35.52% in terms of loan amount disbursed. The shares of SC, ST and OBC category borrowers were 10.79 %, 3.74 % and 20.99 %, respectively, in terms of the loan amount disbursed during 2023-24.

What Steps Have Been Taken to Improve PMMY Scheme

• **Online Application Platforms**

The scheme has integrated online portals like PSBloansin59minutes and Udyamimitra, making it easier for entrepreneurs to apply for loans from the comfort of their homes or offices.

• Also, **MUDRA MITRA** is a mobile app that offers information on MUDRA schemes, guides loan seekers to bankers, and provides loan-related materials and application forms.

• **Publicity Campaigns:** Extensive public awareness campaigns are conducted nationwide to raise awareness about PMMY, ensuring that all eligible entrepreneurs are aware of the scheme and its benefits.

- **Simplified Forms:** The application process has been simplified by streamlining the forms, making them more accessible and less time-consuming for potential borrowers.
- **Nodal Officers:** MUDRA has designated MUDRA Nodal Officers in Public Sector Banks (PSBs) to oversee the scheme's implementation, ensuring effective monitoring and support for applicants.
- **Interest Subvention:** A 2% interest subvention is provided for prompt repayment of **Shishu loans** under **PMMY**, applicable for a period of 12 months to all eligible borrowers.

Achievements of PMMY

Significant Financial Disbursement: As of 13th December 2024, 3.20 crore PMMY loans have been sanctioned, amounting to Rs 3,02,967.03 crore.

Of this, Rs 2,95,808.08 crore has been disbursed, reflecting significant progress under the scheme.

Empowerment of Marginalized Groups: Around 69% of MUDRA loan accounts are held by women, while 51% belong to SC/ST and OBC entrepreneurs, promoting gender equality and social equity.

Boost to Self-Employment: The scheme has encouraged self-employment, particularly in rural and semi-urban areas, fostering small business development and job creation.

Reduced Non-Performing Assets (NPAs): The NPA rate under the scheme dropped from 3.61% in FY21 to 2.1% in FY24, reflecting improved financial discipline among borrowers.

Steady Increase in Lending Exposure: Total MUDRA loan exposure rose from ₹3.3 lakh crore in FY22 to over ₹5 lakh crore in FY24, demonstrating the scheme's expanding reach.

Focus on Rural Inclusion: The scheme has impacted rural entrepreneurs, though unequal regional distribution of credit highlights the need for targeted outreach.

Challenges of PMMY

1. **Loan Quality and NPAs:** A significant portion of loans are small "Shishu" loans (up to ₹50,000), which may not always lead to substantial business transformation. Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) under PMMY have reportedly risen to over 9%, indicating repayment difficulties. Public Sector Banks report a 3.6% gross NPA rate under PMMY (PIB), reflecting concerns over loan repayment and credit risk.
2. **Lack of Business Support:** Many beneficiaries receive credit without adequate training or business support, potentially leading to poor business planning or misuse of funds.
3. **Regional Imbalances:** Disbursements are concentrated in a few states like Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, and Karnataka, while several northeastern states and Union Territories lag significantly in outreach and access.
4. **Over-Indebtedness:** In some areas, such as Maharashtra and Telangana, multiple small loans have resulted in over-indebtedness for borrowers.
5. **Limited Reach to Marginalised Groups:** The scheme struggles to effectively reach women, SC/STs, and remote rural entrepreneurs, despite its inclusive intent.
6. **Loan Limit Constraints:** Even with the ₹20 lakh ceiling for Tarun Plus (from Oct 2024), credit remains inadequate for enterprises requiring higher capital.
7. **Weak Credit Assessment:** Lack of robust creditworthiness checks leads to indiscriminate lending and increases the risk of defaults.
8. **Financial Illiteracy:** Poor financial awareness among borrowers results in the misuse of funds and credit mismanagement.
9. **Funding Gaps:** High demand often exceeds available funds, causing credit shortfalls and leaving many eligible applicants unsupported.

Challenges Faced by Micro-Enterprises:

- Difficulty in accessing finance due to documentation issues, lack of collateral, or credit history.
- Infrastructure gaps like poor roads and unreliable electricity limit business scalability.
- Lack of growth orientation, with many loans supporting subsistence-level businesses rather than expansion.

- Gaps in skill development, financial literacy, and market access for beneficiaries

International Recognition

- The International Monetary Fund (IMF) has consistently acknowledged the impact of the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) in expanding financial access and promoting inclusive entrepreneurship in India.
- In 2017, the IMF noted that the scheme has been instrumental in enabling women-led businesses to access finance. It highlighted how PMMY complements PMJDY's focus on unbanked households by providing collateral-free loans to micro, small, and medium-sized businesses.
- In 2019, the IMF further praised PMMY, stating that the scheme under the Micro Units Development and Refinance Agency plays a vital role in developing and refinancing micro enterprises by supporting financial institutions that lend to businesses engaged in manufacturing, trading and services.
- By 2023, the IMF highlighted that the collateral-free loan structure of PMMY, with its emphasis on women's entrepreneurship, has significantly contributed to the growth of women-owned MSMEs, which now exceed 2.8 million.
- In its 2024 release, the IMF reaffirmed that India's enabling policy environment for entrepreneurship, through programmes such as PMMY, is actively contributing to increased self-employment and formalisation through credit access.

Conclusion

Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana is an initiative by the government to revitalise self-employment opportunities for budding entrepreneurs and the unbanked sector. This scheme promotes financial inclusion to build a strong base for the development of the Indian economy. The study recommends boosting their involvement and customising assistance for entrepreneurs based on regional needs. States like Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, Karnataka, West Bengal and Bihar have been notable in their efforts, with certain districts playing a crucial role. PMMY is not just about providing loans but also stimulating economic growth and empowering individuals across society. The study proposes enhancements to strengthen PMMY's impact, contributing to the broader goal of building an inclusive and equitable economy. The scheme will help the weaker sections, low-income groups, and unfunded populations, and it will also increase competition. Financial inclusion through PMMY increases the opportunities for credit requirements and refinancing. Mudra Yojana will definitely be a positive step taken by the GOI that will take the country forward in the future because it encourages women entrepreneurs as well by refinancing their business plans at a very low rate of interest so that they can generate income and contribute a good amount to the national income. Growth in MSMEs is also a step towards the "Make in India Project", as more domestic industries would lead to more production of indigenous products that compete in foreign markets and create more foreign income, which would improve the value of the rupee, which determines economic growth. So therefore, financial inclusion in MSMEs through this scheme will act as a game changer in the financial market and will boost the Indian economy in the near future.

The scheme has done fairly well, and with the promise of serving to help MSMEs, it has a huge scope to fund the unfunded small entrepreneurs and improve the access of credit to microenterprises. Schemes like PMMY serve as an important tool for small businesses to access commercial capital. However, its success hinges on its design, and with the right mechanism and risk management processes alongside the efficient administration and governing bodies, it can further make the MUDRA scheme financially sustainable, generating positive additionalities.

In ten years, Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana has consistently demonstrated the power of financial inclusion and the strength of grassroots innovation. Before 2014, access to credit often favoured the well-connected, while small entrepreneurs faced hurdles like complex paperwork or were forced to rely on informal finance. Banks handed out reckless loans to large corporates, while genuine borrowers lost access to credit. MUDRA stepped into this vacuum, offering a cleaner, inclusive alternative that gave everyone an equal chance. With over 52 crore loans sanctioned, the scheme has

empowered women, SC/ST/OBC communities, and rural entrepreneurs by expanding access to formal credit. The rise in average loan size, growing share of MSME credit, and the shift from micro to small enterprises reflect its growing impact. PMMY is not only fuelling self-employment and job creation but also strengthening India's grassroots economy and advancing equitable growth.

The study concluded that if Mudra's scheme is implemented in the right way, by providing loans to the right people, it will succeed. The Mudra scheme will add to the well-being of entrepreneurs engaged in micro- and small-scale industries, which will positively shape the progress of the economy as a whole if implemented as per the priority sector lending schemes for the needy and poor. It may work as an important tool for the government in developing nations through financial inclusion and may boost the Indian growth rate of the economy.

Moving forward, the focus for PMMY will likely shift from purely providing loans to building sustainable and scalable businesses. This includes leveraging digital lending solutions for faster credit delivery, improving financial literacy, and strengthening credit support mechanisms to reduce default risks and accelerate the growth of Micro and Small Enterprises.

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